

Projected Changes in Agricultural Drought Severity and Spatial Patterns across Türkiye under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 Scenarios^A

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Abstract: This study evaluates the future impacts of climate change on drought severity across Türkiye using high-resolution climate projections from three Global Climate Models (GFDL-ESM2M, HadGEM2-ES, MPI-ESM-MR) under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Drought conditions were assessed using the 12-month Reconnaissance Drought Index (RDI-12), which integrates both precipitation and evapotranspiration (ET_o), for historical (1971–2000), near-future (2023–2052), and distant-future (2069–2098) periods. The Mann-Kendall test was used to detect trends, while Sen’s slope estimator and spatial visualization techniques were applied to assess the magnitude and spatial distribution of changes. Results indicate a significant increase in drought frequency and severity, particularly under the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Multi-model averages indicate a projected increase of up to 21% in extreme drought frequency (RDI ≤ -2) in the near future under RCP4.5. Central Anatolia, Eastern Mediterranean, and parts of Eastern Anatolia were identified as regions highly vulnerable to intensified drought. Spatial analyses revealed considerable regional heterogeneity, showing varying drought trends depending on the climate model and emission scenario. Overall, the study emphasizes the critical need for region-specific drought mitigation strategies and robust adaptation policies to safeguard agricultural productivity and water resource sustainability under anticipated climate change scenarios.

Keywords: GCMs, GIS, RCP4.5, RCP8.5, spatial analysis, Türkiye

^A The study does not require approval from an ethics committee. The article has been prepared according to research and publication ethics.

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Introduction

Climate change poses a significant threat to global water resources, with far-reaching implications for agricultural sustainability, particularly in regions with vulnerable climatic and hydrological regimes. As global temperatures continue to rise, shifts in precipitation patterns, increased evapotranspiration, and altered hydrological cycles are expected to intensify the frequency and severity of drought events (IPCC, 2021). Among the various manifestations of climate-induced stressors, drought stands out as one of the most complex and least understood phenomena due to its gradual onset, multidimensional impacts, and spatial-temporal variability (Mishra and Singh, 2010; Mehdizadeh et al., 2020).

Drought not only disrupts ecological balances but also jeopardizes food security, water availability, and socio-economic stability, particularly in semi-arid and arid regions (Lesk et al., 2016). The need for robust drought monitoring systems has consequently led to the development of numerous drought indices. Among these, the Reconnaissance Drought Index (RDI), which integrates both precipitation and reference crop evapotranspiration (ET_o), has gained prominence due to its ability to capture climatic water balance variations more comprehensively than precipitation-only indices such as the Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) (Tsakiris et al., 2007; Mahmood et al., 2023).

Türkiye is particularly susceptible to the impacts of climate change due to its diverse topography and transitional climatic characteristics between arid and humid zones. Several studies in Türkiye have applied various drought indices, particularly the RDI, to evaluate meteorological drought under historical climate conditions. Anlı (2014) used the RDI method to analyze drought trends in Southeastern Anatolia and reported increasing drought tendencies based on both parametric and non-parametric trend tests. Yüce and Eşit (2020) assessed drought events in the Ceyhan Basin using ten different indices, including RDI, SPI, and SPEI, and identified strong correlations among them across different time scales. Geyikli et al. (2022) compared SPI and RDI results in the Yeşilirmak Basin and concluded that while both indices yielded similar values during wet periods, RDI more frequently detected severe drought events. Katipoğlu et al. (2022) evaluated drought trends in the Euphrates Basin using multiple indices, including RDI, and applied Mann-Kendall and Modified Mann-Kendall tests, identifying increasing drought frequency across the region. Keşgin et al. (2024) calculated SPI, SPEI, and RDI at multiple time scales using data from 11 meteorological stations along the Mediterranean coast of Türkiye and showed regional drought variability between 1972 and 2020. Şimşek et al. (2024) examined meteorological drought across the Black Sea Region using SPI and RDI, reporting high correlation between the indices, with RDI identifying the most extreme drought risk values. Unlike previous studies, this research provides a comprehensive assessment of future drought severity and spatial variability across Türkiye by integrating three distinct Global Climate Models (GCMs) and two emission scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5). To the best of our knowledge, no prior study has investigated the combined effects of multiple GCMs and emission scenarios on drought dynamics at the national scale using the RDI methodology.

This study aims to investigate the spatial and temporal evolution of drought across Türkiye under future climate conditions by applying RDI to high-resolution outputs of three Global Climate Models (GFDL-ESM2M, HadGEM2-ES, and MPI-ESM-MR) under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. By identifying future drought hotspots and evaluating shifts in drought severity, the study seeks to provide a scientific basis for climate-resilient agricultural planning and sustainable water resource management at the national scale.

Materials and Methods

Study Site

The study was conducted across the entire territory of Türkiye, a country characterized by diverse topography and climatic zones ranging from Mediterranean to continental. To ensure national-scale representativeness, meteorological data from 81 provinces were utilized. The geographical variability of Türkiye plays a crucial role in spatial drought dynamics, making it a suitable case for investigating the regional impacts of climate change on drought severity and trends.

Dataset Description and Future Climate Scenarios

This study evaluates drought severity across Türkiye using model-based climatic data derived from future climate projections. All datasets were generated and provided by the Turkish State Meteorological Service (TSMS). Specifically, projections from three Global Climate Models (GFDL-ESM2M, HadGEM2-ES, and MPI-ESM-MR) were dynamically downscaled to 20 km spatial resolution using the RegCM4.3.4 regional climate model (Akçakaya et al., 2015). Downscaled outputs were extracted for 81 locations, each representing a provincial center, to ensure national-scale spatial coverage.

The reference period was defined as 1971-2000, while future projections were analyzed for the near future (2023-2052) and distant future (2069-2098). These projections were categorized into five scenario groups: RF (reference period), N-45 (near future under RCP4.5), N-85 (near future under RCP8.5), D-45 (distant future under RCP4.5), and D-85 (distant future under RCP8.5).

Drought Index Calculation

To assess agro-meteorological drought, the RDI was used. RDI considers both precipitation and ETo, offering a more comprehensive evaluation of drought severity compared to precipitation-only indices.

Reference crop evapotranspiration was calculated using the FAO-56 Penman-Monteith method via the ETo Calculator software developed by FAO (Allen et al., 1998). This method was selected for its ability to incorporate a range of climatic variables (temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, and solar radiation), providing a physically based and widely accepted standard for ETo estimation in climate change studies.

The standardized RDI values were calculated annually (12-month timescale) for each station using the DrinC software. As a first step, the climatic water balance (a_0) was computed for each station and year using precipitation and ETo values (Equation 1).

$$a_0^{ij} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^k P_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^k ET_{0ij}} \quad (1)$$

Where P_{ij} and ET_{0ij} denote the precipitation and reference crop evapotranspiration (in mm) for the j^{th} month of year i , and $k=12$ for annual aggregation. To standardize the a_0 values and enable temporal comparison of drought severity, a z-score transformation was applied, as described in Equation (2).

$$RDI = \frac{y_k^{(i)} - \bar{y}_k}{\sigma_{y_k}} \quad (2)$$

In this equation, $y_k(i)$ refers to the natural logarithm of a_0 for year i , y_k is the mean, and σ is the standard deviation of the y_k series. This standardization enables the classification of drought severity into defined categories.

Drought classification was based on the standardized RDI thresholds proposed by Nalbantis and Tsakiris (2009). These categories allow for consistent interpretation of drought severity across regions and time periods. The classification thresholds are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Classification of drought severity based on RDI values

RDI Value	Classification
$RDI \geq 0$	No drought
$-1.0 \leq RDI < 0$	Mild drought
$-1.5 \leq RDI < -1.0$	Moderate drought
$-2.0 \leq RDI < -1.5$	Severe drought
$RDI < -2.0$	Extreme drought

Trend Analysis and Spatial Visualization

To identify temporal trends in drought severity, the non-parametric Mann-Kendall test was applied, and trend magnitudes were estimated using Sen's slope estimator (Gilbert 1987).

Spatial interpolation of the RDI values was performed using the Inverse Distance Weighted (IDW) method in ArcGIS 10.2 software. The interpolation was based on outputs from 81 points representing each province, ensuring even administrative coverage across Türkiye. A power value of 2 and 12 neighboring points were used in the interpolation process, following standard practice. IDW was chosen for its computational simplicity and effectiveness in capturing local spatial variability, especially when high-resolution gridded data are unavailable (Rahman et al., 2024). Although geostatistical methods such as Kriging could better represent spatial autocorrelation in heterogeneous terrains, IDW was considered suitable for this study due to its transparent structure and practical applicability with regularly spaced input points. Nonetheless, the limitations associated with IDW, particularly in complex topographies, are acknowledged as a constraint on spatial representativeness.

Results and Discussion

Frequency and Severity of Drought Events

The analysis of drought frequency using the RDI across Türkiye under different climate scenarios and models (GFDL, HadGEM, and MPI under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) reveals significant regional differences and future drought patterns. The RDI values, categorized into varying drought severity classes, indicate distinct temporal and spatial distributions of drought intensity. These variations across Türkiye are visually represented in Figures 1-3, which show the full distribution of annual RDI values for all 81 provinces over each 30-year period and climate scenario, based on the outputs of the GFDL, HadGEM, and MPI models, respectively.

Figure 1. Distribution of annual Reconnaissance Drought Index (RDI) values across 81 provinces of Türkiye under different time-scenario combinations based on the GFDL model: Reference (RF), Near-future RCP4.5 (N-45), Near-future RCP8.5 (N-85), Distant-future RCP4.5 (D-45), and Distant-future RCP8.5 (D-85)

For the GFDL model, the reference period (1971-2000) showed 69 extreme drought occurrences ($RDI \leq -2$). Under the near-future RCP4.5 scenario (N-45), extreme droughts slightly decreased to 62 occurrences, while a further decrease to 56 was noted under the N-85 scenario (Figure 1). However, by the distant future (2069-2098), extreme drought events increased again, particularly under the D-85 scenario, reaching 67 occurrences. This fluctuation may reflect the non-linear interaction between climate variables under different scenarios, though further investigation is needed to identify the underlying causes (Amognehgn et al., 2023).

Figure 2. Distribution of annual Reconnaissance Drought Index (RDI) values across 81 provinces of Türkiye under different time-scenario combinations based on the HadGEM model: Reference (RF), Near-future RCP4.5 (N-45), Near-future RCP8.5 (N-85), Distant-future RCP4.5 (D-45), and Distant-future RCP8.5 (D-85)

For the HadGEM model, the frequency of extreme drought conditions notably increased from 44 events in the reference period to 67 under the N-45 scenario (Figure 2). A further increase to 71 occurrences was projected under D-85 conditions. These findings indicate that severe drought events are expected to become more frequent, particularly under high-emission scenarios, corroborating the increased vulnerability and potential intensification noted by Yüce and Eşit (2020) and Geyikli et al. (2022) for Türkiye.

Figure 3. Distribution of annual Reconnaissance Drought Index (RDI) values across 81 provinces of Türkiye under different time-scenario combinations based on the MPI model: Reference (RF), Near-future RCP4.5 (N-45), Near-future RCP8.5 (N-85), Distant-future RCP4.5 (D-45), and Distant-future RCP8.5 (D-85)

The MPI model depicted a more complex drought pattern. The reference period exhibited 54 extreme drought occurrences (Figure 3). In contrast, the N-45 scenario showed a substantial increase in extreme drought frequency to 73 occurrences, followed by a decrease to 45 under the N-85 scenario (RCP8.5). Similar observations were reported by Wubneh et al. (2024), who identified increased drought frequencies under intermediate emission scenarios due to pronounced regional climatic feedback.

Trend Detection Using Mann-Kendall and Sen's Slope Tests

The temporal trends in annual RDI values were assessed using the non-parametric Mann-Kendall test, while the rate of change was estimated using Sen's slope method. Figure 4 presents the spatial distribution of these results for all five scenarios (RF, N-45, N-85, D-45, D-85) based on the GFDL climate model. Downward and upward triangles indicate decreasing and increasing RDI trends, respectively. Shaded colors represent Sen's slope values, and significance levels are marked at 1% ($p \leq 0.01$), 5% ($p \leq 0.05$), and 10% ($p \leq 0.10$).

While the inclusion of one meteorological station per province ensures a balanced administrative representation across Türkiye, it does not necessarily guarantee full geographical representativeness, especially in regions characterized by complex topography and pronounced microclimatic gradients, such as the Taurus and Pontic mountain ranges. In sparsely monitored or mountainous areas, localized climatic variability may not be adequately captured by centrally located provincial stations. This spatial limitation may influence the precision of interpolated drought patterns, particularly in terrains with high elevation variability. Therefore, the results should be interpreted with this caveat in mind, and future studies would benefit from denser station networks or the incorporation of elevation-dependent climate interpolation techniques.

In the N-45 scenario (Figure 4a), a widespread increasing drought trend is observed across Central Anatolia and the eastern Mediterranean region. Statistically significant negative trends at the 1% and 5% levels were detected in provinces such as Kayseri, Adana, Karaman, and Gaziantep. The slope values in these areas indicate considerable drought intensification. Under the N-85 scenario (Figure 4b), negative trends became even more pronounced, especially in Eastern Anatolia. Provinces like Van and Malatya exhibited statistically significant negative Z-values at the 1% level, reflecting an alarming increase in drought severity under high-emission conditions. In the D-45 scenario (Figure 4c), negative trends continued to dominate Central Anatolia, with some regions in Marmara and the Western Black Sea showing slight positive slopes. However, most of these increases were statistically insignificant. For the D-85 scenario (Figure 4d), drought trends remained negative across much of the country. Although significant patterns were not widespread, strong trends were concentrated in Central Anatolia (particularly in Çankırı, Kırıkkale, and Karaman) where Q values indicated sharp declines in RDI. These findings align with previous regional drought studies (Anlı, 2014; Katipoğlu et al., 2022; Yılmaz, 2023), stating central vulnerability of Anatolia to intensified aridity. During the reference period (RF) (Figure 4e), the most severe drought trends were concentrated in the Marmara and Western Black Sea regions. These areas experienced strong negative slope values, indicating persistent long-term drying. Slightly positive trends observed in Van and Hatay were not statistically significant. Overall, the GFDL model projections indicate a consistent intensification of drought trends, especially under high-emission scenarios. Central and Southeastern Anatolia are projected to be the most vulnerable regions.

Figure 4. Spatial distribution of Mann-Kendall Z-values and Sen's slope (Q) under the GFDL model scenarios (A: Near-future RCP4.5, B: Near-future RCP8.5, C: Distant-future RCP4.5, D: Distant-future RCP8.5, E: Reference period)

The spatial distribution of Mann-Kendall Z-values and Sen's slope (Q) under the HadGEM model is presented in Figure 5. In the N-45 scenario (Figure 5a), the HadGEM model projected more widespread drought intensification compared to GFDL. Statistically significant negative trends were identified across the entire Marmara Region and most provinces along the Black Sea coast, except for Rize, Trabzon, and Artvin. The Konya Basin also exhibited strong drought signals. Trend intensity decreased toward the eastern provinces. Under the N-85 scenario (Figure 5b), the overall spatial extent of drought intensification weakened. Statistically significant trends were mainly limited to Van and Malatya, while western Türkiye showed largely insignificant changes. The D-45 scenario (Figure 5c) revealed a clear spatial divide. Provinces east of a hypothetical Sakarya-Antalya axis showed increasing drought trends, while the northwest (Thrace and northern Aegean) displayed slightly positive or non-significant trends. In D-85 (Figure 5d), no province showed statistically significant intensification at the 1% level. Ardahan exhibited a significant decrease in drought severity at the 5% level. Interestingly, Adana was the only province where a statistically significant reduction in drought (i.e., positive RDI trend) was detected despite the high-emission scenario. During the reference period (RF) (Figure 5e), drought trends were generally weak in both western and eastern Türkiye. However, local intensifications were observed in parts of Central Anatolia and the Middle Black Sea. These spatial patterns are consistent with previous findings by Geyikli et al. (2022), who emphasized the sensitivity of RDI to not only precipitation but also ETo , showing that variations in evapotranspiration may contribute to spatial drought differences; however, the exact mechanisms require more targeted physical analysis.

Figure 5. Spatial distribution of Mann-Kendall Z-values and Sen's slope (Q) under the HadGEM model scenarios (A: Near-future RCP4.5, B: Near-future RCP8.5, C: Distant-future RCP4.5, D: Distant-future RCP8.5, E: Reference period)

Türkiye under five MPI scenarios. In the N-45 scenario (Figure 6a) drought intensity increases over most northern provinces, while parts of the south display weak positive Q values. No province reaches the %1 significance level; only Kırklareli shows a minor (10 %) upward trend, implying locally improving conditions. Under N-85 (Figure 6b) MPI exhibits the largest inter-scenario contrast: drought intensification spreads across almost the entire country except south-eastern Anatolia. The smallest (most negative) Q values occur along the Aegean coast, increasing east-ward, with modest positive trends (up to 0.04) in the south-east. For the D-45 scenario (Figure 6c) pronounced negative trends emerge in eastern provinces, whereas parts of south-western Aegean show slight, non-significant drought relief. The Mediterranean, Marmara, and Black Sea regions remain dominated by negative Q values. The high-emission D-85 scenario (Figure 6d) reinforces these patterns: significant RDI declines (i.e. stronger drought) appear in the Aegean-Marmara belt and the Eastern Black Sea. Conversely, Van, Hatay, and Şanlıurfa record weak but positive Z-scores, indicating isolated reductions in drought severity. During the reference period (RF) (Figure 6e) trends are largely negative in western and central Türkiye, becoming spatially heterogeneous toward the east. The highest positive Q values cluster around the Kars-Iğdır corridor, while the steepest drying trends occur on the eastern flank of Marmara. Collectively, MPI results suggest a potential sensitivity to emission pathways, although further multi-model comparison would be needed to confirm this behavior across different regions and timeframes.

Figure 6. Spatial distribution of Mann-Kendall Z-values and Sen's slope (Q) under the MPI model scenarios (A: Near-future RCP4.5, B: Near-future RCP8.5, C: Distant-future RCP4.5, D: Distant-future RCP8.5, E: Reference period)

Inter-model Divergence and Its Implications

Figure 7 compares the number of extreme-drought years ($RDI \leq -2$) for each model–scenario combination. GFDL and HadGEM exhibit the expected monotonic increase in extreme events from the baseline (RF) through the near-future (N-45, N-85) to the distant-future (D-45, D-85) scenarios. In contrast, the MPI model shows a markedly different trajectory: extreme-drought years peak under the intermediate near-future scenario (N-45) and decline under the high-emission near-future scenario (N-85). This counter-intuitive behavior (fewer extreme droughts under RCP 8.5 than under RCP 4.5) suggests that model-specific land–atmosphere processes or internal variability can modulate the emission-intensity signal. Although identifying the physical drivers of this pattern lies beyond the scope of the present study, its existence showing that inter-model differences are a substantive result in their own right, not merely a source of statistical uncertainty. Future work that couples RDI analysis with circulation diagnostics could clarify whether the MPI response arises from altered precipitation regimes, evapotranspiration feedbacks, or stochastic variability within the model ensemble.

Figure 7. Extreme-drought year counts ($RDI \leq -2$) for each Global Climate Model (RF: Reference, N-45: Near-future RCP 4.5, N-85: Near-future RCP 8.5, D-45: Distant-future RCP 4.5, D-85: Distant-future RCP 8.5).

Climate models often produce divergent drought projections, even under identical emissions scenarios, primarily due to differences in model structure, hydrological sensitivity, and representation of key climate processes (Lu et al., 2019). Specific model choices in simulating precipitation dynamics, evapotranspiration rates, cloud formation, and vegetation responses lead directly to different drought outcomes (Scheff and Frierson, 2015). For example, models with higher evapotranspiration sensitivity or lower precipitation responsiveness to warming generally project more severe drying (Lin et al., 2018). Moreover, differences in representing atmospheric circulation patterns, such as monsoon shifts or subtropical high-pressure expansion, strongly influence regional drought variability among models (Marvel et al., 2019).

An intriguing and somewhat counter-intuitive finding, as observed clearly in MPI-ESM projections and supported by Akram et al. (2024) and Wubneh et al. (2024), is that the moderate emissions scenario (RCP4.5) can occasionally project more severe drought than the higher emissions scenario (RCP8.5) for certain periods. One reason is the differential aerosol forcing: under RCP4.5, aggressive pollution reduction leads to earlier regional warming and higher evaporation rates, temporarily intensifying drought compared to RCP8.5, where sustained higher aerosol concentrations mitigate warming and drought intensity (Lin et al., 2018). Another factor is internal

climate variability—natural fluctuations that dominate near-term climate projections and occasionally produce extreme drought conditions independent of the emissions scenario (Deser et al., 2020). Furthermore, short-term atmospheric circulation anomalies, including intensified El Niño events, can exacerbate drought conditions in moderate emission scenarios (Lyon, 2004).

The MPI model specifically shows more frequent extreme drought events in near-future simulations compared to distant-future scenarios. This outcome likely reflects transient, rapid adjustments of the climate system to initial emission reductions and aerosol declines, along with internal climate variability, rather than a long-term, stable drying trend. Such dynamics illustrate that scenario differences are not linear and straightforward, particularly over shorter-term horizons (Swann et al., 2016). Overall, climate model discrepancies in drought projections arise from fundamental differences in their representation of hydrological and atmospheric processes, and scenario comparisons must carefully consider transient climate responses, internal variability, and aerosol-induced regional warming effects.

Conclusion

This study investigated the projected evolution of drought severity and spatial distribution across Türkiye using the RDI (12-month timescale) under three Global Climate Models and two emission scenarios (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5). The results indicate a notable increase in drought frequency and severity, especially under high-emission conditions. While the percentage of drought-affected years remains around 50%, the frequency of extreme drought events ($RDI \leq -2$) is projected to rise substantially. Central Anatolia and the Eastern Mediterranean, including provinces such as Konya, Van, Malatya, and Gaziantep, consistently emerged as drought vulnerability hotspots across models and scenarios. Although a few provinces (e.g., Edirne, Zonguldak, Bartın) exhibited slight drought relief under certain conditions, overall spatial trends revealed statistically significant increases in drought severity across most of the country.

Unlike previous national-scale studies, this research integrates multiple GCMs, emission scenarios, and a standardized drought index to provide a comprehensive and high-resolution assessment of future drought dynamics. The use of annual RDI allows the evaluation of long-term hydrometeorological drought rather than short-term anomalies, thereby supporting more robust adaptation planning. While the methodology provides valuable insights, limitations such as the use of a single station per province, reliance on the deterministic IDW interpolation method, and uncertainties inherent to climate models should be acknowledged. These factors may affect the spatial accuracy and inter-model comparability of drought projections.

Future research should explore ensemble modeling approaches, integrate land-surface or vegetation indices to link drought with ecological impact, and consider socioeconomic vulnerability metrics to enhance policy relevance. In summary, projected climate-driven drought intensification necessitates proactive regional planning and targeted adaptation strategies. Policymakers and water managers should focus especially on Central Anatolia, Eastern Mediterranean, and Marmara regions, given their pronounced vulnerability.

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